

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

[Network of scientific actors]

SPOKE N 4 – Digital innovation toward sustainable mountain

RM1. Socio-ecological features and opportunities for regeneration in mountain territories

DELIVERABLE DN.1_Network of scientific actors

Task 1.2. Creation of a network of researchers, scholars, and educators responsible throughout the territory for overseeing scientific activities.

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
1	31/10/2023	Final Document	R. Dini, S. Lanteri, C. Dallere (Politecnico di Torino, Dipartimento di Architettura e Design - DAD) P. Giaccaria (UniTO), P. Vesan (UniVDA)

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Contents

GLOSSARY	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
A) 4	
BUILDING A NETWORK	4
MANY VOICES, A SHARED REFLECTION	4
<i>The seminar "Rigenerare comunità, territori e architetture"</i>	8

Glossary

Definition	
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework - NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

A) Network of scientific actors (DELIVERABLE DN.1_RM1)

Task 1.2. Creation of a network of researchers, scholars, and educators responsible throughout the territory for overseeing scientific activities.

Building a network

This first phase was structured following the **construction of a *network*** to support the scientific activities in the area. This **multidisciplinary and multi-scalar** network is conceived to be focused on the theme of **valorisation of *local production chains*** - in particular the one relating to **forestry resources** - as a possible push for **urban-architectural, social and economic regeneration for the territories**; this includes various forms of stakeholders, each of them bringing different but complementary points of view and knowledge: academics, local institutions, professional associations, producers and figures part of the supply chain for transforming raw materials into resources.

Many voices, a shared reflection

This work was articulated through a series of meetings with variable dimensions, with different figures meeting and starting to create a shared debate on the topic in different ways, online and in person, on several occasions consistently over the months.

The conference "Rigenerare comunità, territori, architetture" - curated and organized by RM1 as a founding moment of the network - took place on 27 October 2023 in Saint-Marcel (Aosta) and introduced for the first time the co-presence of all the subjects involved, trying to systematize and publicly share the premises of a common reflection. It was therefore conceived as a moment of synthesis of the previous choral reflections, a moment of closure of the first step of work which is followed by the opening of the new phase of research.

Below is the network of scientific, technical and institutional stakeholders involved in this first meeting:

Politecnico di Torino (DAD) – Roberto Dini, Silvia Lanteri, Cristian Dallere
Università di Torino (ESOMAS) – Paolo Giaccaria
Università della Valle d'Aosta – Patrik Vesan
Regione Autonoma Valle d'Aosta – Dipartimento Risorse naturali e Corpo forestale
Comune di Saint-Marcel (AO)
Consorzio Enti locali della Valle d'Aosta – CELVA
GAL Valle d'Aosta
Ordine degli Architetti della Valle d'Aosta
Ordine dei Dottori Agronomi e dei Dottori Forestali della Valle d'Aosta
Andrea Bionaz – Sindaco Comune di Saint-Marcel
Marco Carrel - Assessorato regionale all'Agricoltura e Risorse naturali, Regione Autonoma Valle
d'Aosta
Corrado Cremonini, Francesco Negro, Roberto Zanuttini, UniTO
Stephan Kampelmann, Sonian Wood, Université Libre de Bruxelles
Guido Callegari, PoliTO
Francesco Loreggian, Università di Padova
Terra di casa Coop - Rete SI parte dal bosco
Piero Brunod, Host'Hello, Nus
Carlo Boccazzi Varotto, Hackability
Igor Vigna, Consorzio Forestale del Canavese
Julien Cerisey, Estrabocon, Saint-Oyen – Aosta
Didier Contoz, L'Arsalé, Nus – Aosta

27 ottobre 2023 h 9
Municipio di
Saint-Marcel

mattina momento seminariale
pomeriggio talk itinerante nella/sulla foresta

rigenerare comunità, territori, architetture

L'incontro ha l'obiettivo di avviare una riflessione multidisciplinare sul tema della valorizzazione delle filiere produttive locali (in particolare quella relativa alla risorsa forestale) come possibile motore di rigenerazione urbana-architettonica, sociale ed economica per il territorio. Il seminario del mattino sarà un momento di incontro tra esperti che condivideranno potenzialità e problematiche connesse alla necessità di mettere a sistema valorizzazione delle risorse produttive locali, culture costruttive e riqualificazione di spazi a servizio delle comunità. Nel pomeriggio, attraverso un'escursione nei boschi di Saint-Marcel guidata da professionisti del settore, si avrà l'occasione di approfondire il tema della risorsa forestale locale, in relazione allo sviluppo di scenari futuri.

Evento promosso dal Politecnico di Torino - Dipartimento di Architettura e Design - centro di ricerca *Istituto di Architettura Montana*
Con il patrocinio di Regione Autonoma Valle d'Aosta
Comune di Saint-Marcel
GAL Valle d'Aosta
Consorzio degli Enti Locali della Valle d'Aosta - CELVA
Ordine degli Agronomi e Forestali - Valle d'Aosta
Ordine degli Architetti - Valle d'Aosta

La partecipazione al convegno riconosce:
- nr. CFP 0,875 SDAF 19 per la categoria dei Dott. Agronomi e Dott. Forestali/Rif Regolamento per la formazione professionale continua approvato con delibera del Consiglio n. 162 del 27 aprile 2022
- nr. CFP 4 per l'Ordine degli Architetti, per la partecipazione alla mattinata.

L'incontro è parte dell'attività di ricerca del Flagship project 3: INTERFACE - Participatory and digital Ecological Transition For mountain Communities, Research Module 1 - New Socio-ecological features as opportunities for regeneration in mountain territories, Ecosistema dell'Innovazione "Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile" - NODES - Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza (PNRR), Missione 4 Istruzione e ricerca - Componente 2 Dalla ricerca all'impresa - Investimento 1,5, contratto n.ECS00000036

con il patrocinio di:

Seminario
09:00 - 13:00

09:00 – 09:15 Saluti istituzionali, e introduzione di
Andrea Bionaz - Sindaco di Saint-Marcel e di
Marco Carrel - Assessore regionale all' Agricoltura e Risorse naturali
09:15 – 09:30 Introduzione al seminario,
Roberto Dini, PolITO
09:30 – 10:00 *Prospettive e criticità nella
valorizzazione del legno locale,*
Corrado Cremonini, Francesco Negro, Roberto Zanuttini, UniTO
10:00 – 10:30 *Sonian Wood – Constructions en bois et économie circulaire,*
Stephan Kampelmann, Université Libre de Bruxelles
10:30 – 11:00 *Tecnologia del legno e progetto di architettura,*
Guido Callegari, PolITO
11:00 – 11:30 *L'unione fa la forza: soluzioni e strumenti associativi a
supporto della gestione forestale,*
Francesco Loreggian, Università di Padova
11:30 – 12:00 *Dal bosco alla casa,*
Terra di casa Coop - Rete SI parte dal bosco
12:00 – 12:30 *Il ruolo della comunità locale,*
Paolo Giaccaria, UniTO
12:30 – 13:00 *Prospettive di economia sociale,*
Patrik Vesan, UniVDA
modera: Silvia Lanteri, PolITO

pausa pranzo
13:00 – 14:30

Escursione e visita guidata alla risorsa forestale locale
14:30 – 17:30

Introduce: Piero Brunod
Intervengono:
L'esperienza del Consorzio Forestale del Canavese,
Igor Vigna
Julien Cerisey, Estrabocon, Saint-Oyen - Aosta
Didier Contoz, L'Arsalé, Nus - Aosta
modera: Cristian Dallere, PolITO

righe - nerare comu - nità, territori, architet - ture

con il patrocinio di:

The seminar "Rigenerare comunità, territori e architetture"

The day was divided into two moments: the morning at the Saint-Marcel town hall, a conference with various institutions and researchers part of the network; the afternoon instead proposed an itinerant dialogue within some areas that were the subject of reflection. The day was moderated by Politecnico di Torino - Roberto Dini, Silvia Lanteri, Cristian Dallere.

The first interventions (*Corrado Cremonini*, researcher at the Department of Agricultural, Forestry and Food Sciences - Unito; *Stephan Kampelmann*, Sonian Woods - ULB) deal precisely with the theme of **valorising local forest resources** through initiatives that aim to increase skills and interaction between different operators involved in the supply chain. The interventions focus attention on wood as a strategic resource at the center of a productivity system that needs to be rethought; we therefore intend to highlight the critical issues and **limitations due to the current constraints, but also potential and possible development prospects through the aggregation of the actors in the supply chain and the use of forestry certifications.**

The complex theme of "**building with wood**" is then discussed (*Guido Callegari*, associate professor at the Department of Architecture and Design - Polito) **as a characterizing element of the Alpine and Apennine landscapes of our country**, the result of the superposition of a cultural dimension but also scientific-technological in transition and transformation, **capable of regenerating territories through an ecosystemic vision of living.** He therefore tries to retrace the main stages of the evolutionary path of this sector over the last twenty years in order to understand the skills and values that have generated new job prospects around the different local identities in Italy and abroad.

We continue (*Francesco Loregian*, PhD student at the Department of Territory and Agro-Forestry Systems - Unipd) investigating the topic of **possible forest management tools in associative form** oriented towards reducing costs and increasing opportunities for valorising ecosystem services bypassing the consistent problem of property fragmentation. By associative form, we mean the associations and aggregations both between the owners of the forests and between the subsequent actors in the supply chain.

Following, we have the story of the ten-year experience of a cooperative (*Diana Sartori and Luca Malavolta* - Cooperativa Terra di Casa, Si parte dal Bosco) in the **use of local ties in the construction sector**, moving from the first supply chain experience to the establishment of a business network. The aim of this intervention is to highlight through a series of stories and projects how essential it is to adopt a **systemic and multidisciplinary approach for the protection and valorisation of forest resources.**

To close the morning of speeches (*Paolo Giaccaria*, associate professor at the Department of Economic-Social and Mathematical-Statistical Sciences - Unito; *Patrik Vesan*, associate professor at the Department of Economic and Political Sciences - Univda), the themes of **co-designing** and **involvement of local communities in the processes of territorial transformation and regeneration**, concluding with some reflections that touch on the topic of **social economy prospects** in this dimension.

In the afternoon the event moves **to the field** within a wooded area owned by the municipality of Saint-Marcel, up to the mountain. The meeting takes place through a four-voice debate regarding the **critical issues and interests of different professionals in a wooded area** with specific characteristics for the activation of a supply chain process. Speakers include *Jean Claude Haudemand* (manager of the Forestry and Trails office of the Agriculture and Natural Resources Department of the Valle d'Aosta Autonomous Region), *Igor Vigna* (technical and administrative manager of the Canavese Forestry Consortium), *Julien Cerisey* (owner of the Estrabocon sawmill) and *Didier Contoz* (owner of the forestry company L'Arsalé).

